

Capacity Building For Inclusive Sustainable Development In Business: How Well Has Nigeria Oil And Gas Fared Under President Tinubu's Administration?

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the administration of Tinubu's capacity building for sustainable development in area of oil and gas production in Nigeria. It took a stance on the campaign promises of the administration that they will empower the citizenry through capacity building in education and skill acquisition to take lead in innovation and obtain competitive advantage. Several forms of capacity building were evaluated and the causes of illegal oil bunkering in the oil rich region x-rayed. Government's efforts to eliminate this clog on economic wheel of the nation was brought to limelight and literature evidence on why illegal bunkering has remained hydra-headed was noted. The study concluded that adequate funding, education, business startups with training and retraining are all important to creating innovative and resilient people that will improve their competitive edge and make an environmental friendly contribution to the socioeconomic measure of the nation.

Keywords: Capacity Building, Sustainable Development, Oil Bunkering, Training and Retraining

INTRODUCTION

The present administration in Nigeria came into power in 2023 with the promise of capacity building through empowering its youths to create, manufacture and invent more of the goods and services consumed, providing electricity for all and train the poor and vulnerable while providing them with economic opportunities. Removal of fuel subsidy was its priority to utilize the fund in support of agriculture, road construction, education and healthcare programs. The difficult economic position in Nigeria is one important change since the new government took office in 2023 with records of dwindling economic indices like rising unemployment and underemployment [1]; Increased poverty and food insecurity [2]; fuel subsidy removal and fuel price hike [3]; 33.95% Soaring inflation rates [1]. The problems, in turn, have hurt the country's macroeconomic performance and social and economic landscape. It is believed that the government's capacity building promises to its people would align perfectly well with the ideology and intention of this conference that is anchored on capacity building for inclusive sustainable development. But the government has kept up with its type of economic reforms, such ending the petroleum subsidy, to deal with social and economic problems, make the most of the country's potential, and reach important development goals. Nonetheless, the reforms seems to be suppressing overall economic outcomes which provokes the question whether capacity building for sustainable development is really effected in programs and reforms of the government? It was expected that local refineries in the nation would be made to function

again, so that their operations could douse the high rate on imported petrol which is majorly the reason for high inflation rate in the country [4].

The trend in competition on global economy necessitates nations, organisations and individuals to enhance their competencies and capabilities to remain competitive in their area. Nigeria is major exporter of crude oil but imports refined petroleum from foreign nations while abandoning four government owned refineries. This study focusses on the oil and gas sector since it brings in the most foreign exchange (over 90%), makes up approximately 5.5% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and brings in around 87% of the Federal Government's recoverable revenue [1]. Also, oil makes up more than 78% of our country's commercial energy use and has been the engine of growth, powering the whole economy. Capacity building with respect to oil and gas sector requires the nation to reform the operations within the sector, by stopping all imports of the refined products, engage its people in the refining process for greater employment creation.

A nation or organisation's capacity building stems from its programs geared towards achieving its objectives. For organisations to set up strategies that will ensue their continued relevance to the society, they must be able to change with the changes in societal demands and ideologies which can be possible if only they tilt to improving their strength and exploiting the opportunities within their space, which is termed capacity building. [5] defines capacity building as the act of improving and developing the skills, instincts, abilities, processes,

and resources that organisations and communities need to survive, adapt, and prosper in a world that is changing quickly. From the above [5] perspective, capacity building appears to be the key to organisational innovativeness, a strategy for being productive and means of harnessing skills and resources that abound to them in order to gain competitive advantage. Put differently, capacity building emerges as the process through which individuals get empowered with the required skills and knowledge for proficiencies in their professions [6]. Be that as it may, it becomes imperative to uphold that capacity building is the activation of the growth prospects in individuals by acquainting them with new knowledge, skills and resources to become efficient and proficient in their operations. Hence, we should be convinced that capacity building is the key to providing empowerment to individuals, attaining self-sufficiency by communities and re-positioning organisations and individuals to being competitive as well as taking the market lead. If this is done, government can eliminate illegal oil bunkering in the **sector** by rebuilding the capacity of the perpetrators, and empowering them in legit profession as well as dealing decisively with dissidents.

On the other hand, Sustainable development concept arose because actions and aspirations of many actors (stakeholders) on earth has far reaching consequences on other part of the globe. As a matter of fact, pollutant in one area causes dangerous impact on distant locations, while deforestation in certain location negatively exposes some other inhabitants to bad weather [7], while oil spillage from illegal bunkering pollutes the environment and destroys traditional source of livelihood to local dwellers [8]. The government has the obligation of making policies with strict implementations, regulating operations of its citizens with respect to environmental pollution, emissions and waste disposals as well as encourage all to adopt environmental friendly practices. For instance, with abundant sunlight, wind and gas resources in the nation, investing in solar, wind energy and gas turbine can boost power generation and reduce dependency on fossil fuels (non-renewable) that generates carbon dioxide. This will also assist in meeting the present needs without compromising or exhausting the non-renewable fossil fuel that would impair the ability of future generation from meeting their own needs. The study result would assist the present government of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu to redefine his policies especially in strategizing to building capacity of the people of oil rich region and adopting them into the main stream refining activities of the nation, so as to end or reduce drastically the menace of oil theft and increase the revenue of the nation. Nonetheless, the study had also added to the existing literature that gave insight on the realizable solution to illegal bunkering in oil sector. This paper

covers a period from 2023-2025 in Nigeria oil and gas and concentrates on activities of Government that could improve capacity building in this sector without impairing the growth of other sectors, hence the importance and urgency of the paper to awaken the government agencies and policy makers to judiciously empower the citizens. Be that as it may, the research did not engage quantitative evidence to test the extent the government policy focus had empowered lives of the oil rich region because very few private refineries were given operating license.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

[8] investigated the effect of illegal oil bunkering on national security in the Niger Delta region on the research design of mixed method. The study covered the population of 31,224,587 persons while Taro Yamane was employed for determination of sample size of 400 household heads. Three hundred and twelve of the instruments administered were collected back and eighteen persons were interviewed for the qualitative part. The data so collected were analysed using percentages and frequencies and the interview information was thematically analysed. The outcome show that pervasive impact of illegal oil bunkering on human and national security underscores a complex web of challenges. Therefrom the study recommends that Nigerian government and other African nations in the Gulf of Guinea should apply satellite technology to track all cargo and crude oil boats operating in the sub-region. [9] investigated the effect of capacity building as a strategic tool for innovation and sustainability.

The objectives included to evaluate the effect of capacity building practices on innovation and sustainability; and determination of the relationship between human resource development and employee's commitment to innovation. Eight hundred (800) senior and junior staff of selected food and beverage companies in southwest Nigeria constituted the population, sample size of three hundred and sixty three (363) was determined, while using proportionate random sampling technique in selection of samples. The study employed survey research design and data collected from the selected sample of selected food and beverage companies were analysed using descriptive statistics, regression, and correlation analysis. The result show that capacity building practices adopted by the study firm had a slight impact on innovation. More so, the study found that capacity building practices did not affect sustainability. [10] evaluated the association between oil theft and insecurity in post amnesty era in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria from the perspective of national security. The study adopted the use secondary data and came out with the findings that militancy and economic sabotage in oil rich region was caused by unemployment, land degradation, resource control, under-development and poverty.

The study concludes that without addressing the root cause as mentioned, any measure of solution would be like a palliative to the problems and can only affect the surface. It recommends that government should provide employments and reduce poverty that is striking badly on the people. [11] overviewed how entrepreneur could be developed in a sustainable was capacity building in Nigerian economy. The study looked at several forms entrepreneur's capacity could be built including through traditional education, vocational training, on the job training, classroom training, off the job training and electronic training. It further called up certain problems facing entrepreneurs in Nigeria and conclude that government should provide adequate funds for the entrepreneurship to thrive and drive the economy to becoming competitive amongst the comity of nations. [12] looked at capacity building as a way to teach teachers in Mexico about sustainable development.

The Sustainable Campus Programme coordinator asked four faculty members to help make the "Educate-the-Educator's" course on sustainable development. Lectures, readings, role-playing games, homework, and class discussions were all part of the course. Also, the course included a workshop structure that helped teachers include themes of sustainable development in their own classes. The study found that a course that is developed and taught by people from many different fields is a good way to teach teachers about sustainable development. Writing down specific parts of the learning process helped both the "students" and the course leaders comprehend the whole thing better. [13] evaluated a research agenda that is based on developing capabilities and competence for sustainable business management as innovation. Empirical studies reviewed by the study indicate that sustainable innovation could be achieved through a multifaceted network of actors while holding local knowledge as the bedrock for innovative breakthrough. Additionally, the study also points out that there is a systemic failure to address the requirement for creativity as a key part of innovation. The study suggests parts of an applied research agenda to help us learn more about the skills that help businesses innovate in ways that are better for the environment. [14] analysed the role of education in capacity building including the capabilities that can allow people to control environment, adapt to the environment to fulfill his responsibilities. Haven x-rayed the forms of education at peoples disposal, the study concludes that education plays a vital role in the development, improvement and strengthening people's capacity to keep the nation on the track of prosperous life.

Knowledge gap: the literature reviewed is indicative that prior studies mostly linked capacity building to sustainable development and competitive edge on

broad perspective. It was discovered that none had specifically x-rayed governments response to the capacity building promises they made during campaign periods. Hence, this study checked the adherence of President Tinubu's administration in fulfilling his capacity building promises to Nigerians, with emphasis on the illegal bunkering crisis prone oil rich region in Nigeria. Therefore this knowledge was filled by the study.

FORMS OF CAPACITY BUILDING IN BUSINESS

Educational Acquisition

One powerful means of empowering the populace is to allow them the opportunity of having access to quality education. The option of this capacity building is in congruence with United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4, to ensure inclusive and quality education that promotes lifelong learning opportunities for all [15]. Youth of the nation are earnestly striving for academic empowerment even when government have no serious plans to liberate its citizens academically. Acquiring quality education prepares the acquirers for challenges and opportunities in the future. It provides the people with the capacity of being exposed to digital literacy to take advantage of the socio-technological driven opportunities across the globe. Education can improve the strength and capabilities in individuals, fostering job satisfaction and self-confidence. Capacity building through education exposes the youth to offshore jobs as well as local jobs. However, Nigerian youth have made impressive records on attaining educational empowerment both at local and international schools.

According to [16], about seventy one thousand seven hundred and fifty three (71,753) Nigerians are studying abroad. Such exposition will be a viable building block to enhancing strategic risk management skills for several administrative positions and ensuring long-term profitability of organisations they may lead. In 2024 fiscal year, Nigeria allocated N2.18 trillion to education sector which represented 7.9% of its total budget. This shows that more needed to be done to build the capacity of Nigerian youths educationally since the budget to education is far below UNESCO's recommended 15-20% [17]. More disturbing was the report and fact that national assembly's allocation in 2024 budget, was obviously meant to be higher than total allocations to twenty six (26) federal universities in Nigeria, a strategic trend that has undermined capacity building through education in the nation [18]. If the nation can reverse the pattern of its approach to educational empowerment, they can be assured to unlocking potentials for innovation on circular economic models that can embrace green technologies and sustainable product designs, which can lead to new product lines, innovative business

models, access to new market and better access to funding.

Training and Retraining

Training and retraining are important tools to capacity building in any business venture. The two are like Siamese twin to business successes by enhancing employees' skills fostering innovation and improving productivity and enabling the business retain competitiveness in a fast changing global market. It is the act of training and retraining that can enable the businesses enhance operational efficiency and pose resilience before any internal and external threats, training and retraining equips people with knowledge and skills development including their foundational knowledge, technical skills, soft skills and ensured maximum compliance to legal-ethical requirements and management of operational risk. For instance, there was a report of Anambra state government initiative of one youth two skills programs that was targeted to ensuring that youths of the state obtain required skills that would help them soar higher in life [19, 20]. Ideally, retraining becomes imperative when employees skills are obsolete emanating from technological advancement, market shift and change in operation (automation). Pertinently, retraining enhances workers flexibility that enable them take up divergent roles in the organisation which fosters productivity and going concern of the business. Training and retraining exercise as tools for capacity building are engine that stimulates innovation, repositions the organisation to maintain competitive advantage and ensures cost saving in their operations. In which case, the government can do a lot more towards training and retraining her citizens for sustainable development in strategic positioning.

Business Start-Ups

Capacity building through business start-ups entails empowering the people towards driving sustainable development that fosters job creation, economic growth, and social inclusion. Startup as a capacity building synchronizes with economic growth of United Nations Sustainability Development Goals (SDGs) 8 of creation of sustained employment and nurturing innovation that guarantee decent work for all; SDG 10 enabling economic opportunities to the marginalized groups by reducing economic inequalities amongst citizens; and SDG 13 which set for actions to fight climate change and establishing green products and services [15]. Business startups reserves the potential to expand entrepreneurial skills development, foster innovation and technological transfer with a powerful knowledge sharing ecosystem. Igbos are the typical users of this business startup ideology in their local parlance apprenticeship (Igba odibo). Upon this program, the new entrant or young one learns the trade/skill and the boss will fund him to start operating on his own, to which

settlement would be done at the agreed time period. [21] referred to this business operation amongst the Igbos as the largest business incubation program throughout the entire the universe. This approach to capacity building strengthens community driven enterprises as well as uplifts marginalized groups in the society. Notwithstanding the height attained by business startups to capacity building, it still faces such problems as not having access to sizeable fund that would enable them engage in sustainable innovations associated with green products, insufficient technical knowledge in sustainable productions, serious regulatory barriers that predominates the region, trust issues, dishonesty which emanated from fraudulent attitude of some trainees that defrauded their boss. The challenges were summarised to include abandoning formal education, lacking government support and lacking certification [22]. It is noteworthy that if government can step in to augment what individuals are doing to sustain business startups in ways of accessible grants, partnerships, there would be a significant impact in capacity building amongst the citizenry and the nation especially in sustainable practices.

Funding

Visions and dreams could be very lofty but when lack financial resources for execution, becomes a wishful thinking. Attainment of capacity built through training, education and skill acquisition could only be meaningful when required fund avails for proper kick off, hence funding becomes a central lubricant for capability building and innovational development. In the opinion of [23], funding is an essential factor for new business kick offs, introduction of new product line or expansion of existing business. For efficient compliance to environmental friendly products, fund will be required to acquire equipment needed for the ecofriendly and energy-saving operations (renewable energy solutions). Most financial challenge of firms lies in inability to cover due short term obligations because of insufficient cash haven invested on equipment [24]. Be that as it may, the training and retraining exercise for easy application of advanced technological innovations and adaptations to green operations are capital intensive exercises that requires heavy funding. Pertinently, a firm or individual would have no capacity to build financial resilience if he operates on a financially quake state. In all, building solid financial system will enable business acquire the right circular economic model that drives sustainability and viably repositions the firm for competitive advantage.

Problem of Oil and Gas in Nigeria

Bunkering activities in oil rich region of Nigeria: The oil producing region of Nigeria once had massive oil sabotage from early 2000, prompted by illegal oil bunkering which were undertaken by **unemployed youths** of host communities to fend for themselves

and their dependent relatives [25]. According to [26], the overboard socio-economic problem of sabotage in oil rich region of Nigeria is ornamented by systemic corruption, powered by scarce economic opportunities and metaphase to active environment for illegal bunkering businesses. The accusation of government and companies operating on oil rich region of neglect and non-provision of employment is so strong that the perpetrators of illegal bunkering openly confess that lack of jobs prompted them engage in illegal bunkering as means of livelihood [27, 28, 29]. In the words of [30], he classified illegal bunkering as oil theft that has been the bane of stealing crude oil in the Niger Delta region for local and foreign markets. In 2023 financial year, it was reported that Nigeria lost about 400,000 barrel of crude oil per day amounting to US\$1.7 billion each month. However, government of President Goodluck Jonathan once floated amnesty program for the unemployed youth which saw drastic reduction on the economic sabotage of illegal bunkering [10], and increased the daily production level of crude oil. Notwithstanding, [31] noted that few miscreants that were not paid and not having jobs took to creeks after the amnesty and resumed illegal bunkering activates to pursue prosperity. There is also an indication that youths from other geo-political zones get attracted to lucrative activities of the bunkering business and are recruited for oil theft for self-enrichment and economic empowerment [10].

Pertinently, the **marginalization** or total neglect of the oil producing region in developmental and infrastructural designs of the nation, forced the communities to engage in oil theft and use proceed for job creation and provision of basic necessities that ought to have been provided by federal government [32]. These acts give a pointer that government has much to do in areas of capacity building and empowerment to the youths that sabotage the main source of revenue of the nation so as to have them gainfully engaged within or outside the sector.

Environmental pollution and degradation in oil rich region: Environmental Degradation emanating from Oil spills and gas flaring are common occurrences in the Niger Delta region, and these activities cause significant environmental damage, affecting water sources, soil, and air quality. Crude oil theft involves breaking of pipelines and siphoning of crude oil products which invariably leads to oil facilities damages and oil spillages that causes degradation of the environment; destruction of farm lands and forests thereby reducing arable land for farming [33]. Spills into water ways destroy marine and aquatic life, flora, fauna, resort centers and result in the pollution of potable water [34, 35]. This pollution has severe consequences on the health and livelihoods of local communities [36, 37], including their farming business which pave way for sourcing for alternative

means of livelihood, hence more reasons for oil theft or bunkering activity.

Finally, Corruption in the system: Corruption within the sector, including contract awards and revenue collection, undermines transparency and accountability. Partly, corruption in the nation becomes the contributor for inconsistent regulations and a lack of enforcement that create uncertainty and hinder investment. It has been established that various interest foreigners, communities members, government agencies and authorities are partners in Nigerian oil bunkering activities which makes it difficult to be checkmated [38].

What Has Government Done To Forestall Illegal Activities In Oil Sector

Deployment of National Production Monitoring System (NPMS): The Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR) had introduced this monitoring system as an accounting solution to ensure transparency, eliminate crude oil and gas theft as well as ascertain the actual crude oil production of the nation per day [39].

Launched an app for monitoring crude oil theft: the government has launched an app that facilitates monitoring of crude oil facilities on Friday 12th, August 2022 [40]. The app is to give signals to the host communities when any attempt is made on any facility while the member of the host community would then file reports to the relevant security authority. Nonetheless, the app is more like a whistle blowing support to the host community.

The creation of the Nigeria Maritime Administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA) to oversee maritime activities; the Joint Task Force (JTF); the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC); the passing of laws like the Oil Pipeline Act and the Oil Theft and Pipeline Vandalism Act; and the establishment of the Ministry of Niger Delta Affairs to deal with the root causes of militancy and illegal bunkering [27]. Still, there hasn't been any real or important change; for example, NNPC reported that 600,000 barrels of oil were stolen per day in 2023 [41].

The Nigerian Navy is using new technology and radar surveillance to improve maritime security and increase sea patrols. They have also set up an Inter-Agency Maritime Operations Coordination Committee (IMOCC) to help agencies working in the industry work together to make sure the safety and security of the Nigerian maritime industry. Additionally, modern aircraft with Nigerian pilots trained under the Petroleum Technology Development Fund (PTDF) program are providing air surveillance of Nigeria's pipelines [42].

The proposed cleaning of Ogoni land: government's plan to clean Ogoni land of environmental population

to enable them recommence agricultural activities has been on paper for long. However, certain preliminary stages of that cleaning has been done and presently, government is set to undertake Hydrocarbon Pollution Remediation, a high risk complex sites where the soil and ground water were contaminated within residential area [43]. The ministry of environmental had taken a decision to the best global innovative technology in executing the projects. It is obvious that comprehensive cleaning of Ogoni land would cause many agribusiness to return to the area thereby enabling many jobless people that are engaged in bunkering acts to have viable alternative legit business pursuit.

The government of Nigeria must take a multifaceted, pragmatic approach focused on infrastructure development, anti-theft enforcement, technical investment, and regulatory change in order to remove obstacles in the country's oil and gas activities. The Petroleum Industry Act (PIA), which provides a thorough structure to improve governance, lessen corruption, and increase investor trust in the industry, is an essential first step [44]. Addressing the pervasive problem of oil theft and pipeline vandalism is crucial in addition to regulatory reform. Because of poor enforcement and insufficient surveillance, Nigeria is said to lose more than 400,000 barrels of crude oil every day as a result of sabotage and theft [45]. These losses can be considerably reduced by implementing contemporary technologies like drones, satellite monitoring, and community-based security systems. Additionally, funding the modernisation and restoration of deteriorating infrastructure, such as refineries and pipelines, will lessen operating downturn and Nigeria's excessive reliance on imported refined goods. Nigeria's oil output and economic returns have long been hampered by infrastructure limitations, according to [46]. The Nigerian government may improve the oil and gas sector's contribution to national development by addressing these important challenges at the same time and restoring stability and efficiency.

CONCLUSION

Capacity building should be targeted to all citizens on productive age and should be navigated towards environmentally friendly activities. The efforts of the government to revamp and regain total control of crude oil producing region that is majorly its source of revenue has met with stiff resistance, an indication of lack of political power to enforce action, and portrays involvement of those in corridors of power as well as deepens the shallow empowerment programs of the government. Government should note that funding is not merely financial support but a strategic tool for building businesses that are resilient, innovative and sustainable. More so, trainings and retraining of people should not be seen as operational necessity but a learning that builds innovativeness

and makes people possess adaptive ability to new technologies as to maintain competitiveness advantage. Finally, the present government has done little to change the narratives of the activities of vandals in the oil rich region. Most of the activities and policies of the government to revitalize the oil sector ends in paper. For example, the Senate committee on local content just recently commended President Bola Tinubu on his efforts to deepen local participation in Nigeria's oil and gas industry [47]. However, the effect of all these media jingles are yet to seen. They should know that when the youth with skills on refining have been empowered or adopted into formal refining operation of the nation, with stringent punishment for offenders, the illegal bunkering would definitely be a thing of the past.

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